

**ARSENIC ACCUMULATION IN RICE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE
EFFECTS OF GLOBAL WARMING AND A MICROBIAL APPROACH TO
ARSENIC BIOREMEDIATION**

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Abstract

Arsenic (As) is a carcinogenic metalloid that poses a serious threat to environmental and public health. Due to global warming, the reduction of water resources and the increased use of arsenic-contaminated deep groundwater in agriculture have led to critical levels of arsenic accumulation in rice cultivation. This study examines the natural forms of arsenic, its relationship with global warming, the current situation in Türkiye, and the potential of microbial bioremediation as an environmentally friendly remediation strategy. Research findings indicate that the isolation of arsenic-resistant bacteria and their application in biotechnological processes are essential for sustainable food safety.

Keywords: Arsenic, Global Warming, Rice, Bioremediation, Food Safety

1. Arsenic: A Global and Toxicological Profile

1.1. Nature and Oxidation States of Arsenic

Arsenic (As) is a metalloid that occurs naturally in gray, yellow, and black forms [1]. It has been known since the Bronze Age (ca. 2500 BCE) and was first isolated by Albertus Magnus in 1250. Arsenic exists in four different oxidation states in nature [1]:

- arsine [As(-III)]
- elemental arsenic [As(0)]
- arsenite [As(III)]
- arsenate [As(V)]

Among these, As(III) (arsenite) is significantly more toxic than As(V). The solubility of arsenic depends on environmental pH and ionic conditions, while As(V) is considered the most stable form, which is critical for microbial remediation processes [1, 2, 3].

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1.2. Sources and Distribution:

Arsenic is the 20th most abundant element in the Earth’s crust. Its release into the environment occurs through both natural processes (volcanic activity and weathering) and anthropogenic activities [1, 4]. Major anthropogenic sources include:

- Use of pesticides and herbicides [5]
- Wood preservatives and paint materials [6]
- Mining and smelting operations [6]

1.3. Public Health and Toxicity:

Arsenic is classified as a Group I human carcinogen and is toxic to all forms of life, including microorganisms. Species that cannot detoxify arsenic cannot survive. It enters the human body primarily through drinking water and contaminated food. Chronic exposure may lead to skin lesions (hyperpigmentation), white lines on nails (Mee’s lines), gangrene, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and various cancers (lung, skin, bladder) [7].

2. Global Warming, Water Crisis, and Risks in Rice Cultivation

2.1. Impact of Global Warming on Arsenic Pollution: Global warming disrupts the water cycle through climate change. Increasing temperatures lead to the depletion or drying of surface water resources, thereby increasing the concentration of pollutants. This situation necessitates the use of deep groundwater, which may contain high levels of arsenic and is often insufficiently monitored for agricultural use.

2.2. Relationship Between Rice and Arsenic: Although rice is one of the most widely consumed foods globally, it is also the crop that accumulates the highest levels of arsenic among cereals. The main reasons include:

- Intensive water use in rice cultivation
- Increased bioavailability of arsenic in waterlogged soils (paddy fields)
- Rice paddies contributing approximately 40% of methane emissions (a greenhouse gas)

This creates a feedback loop in which global warming increases arsenic contamination, while increased contamination further contributes to global warming through methane emissions.

2.3. Current Situation in the World and Türkiye: Millions of people worldwide are affected by arsenic contamination. For example, approximately 57 million people in Bangladesh are exposed due to contaminated wells. Türkiye is also under similar

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threat, particularly in provinces such as İzmir, Kütahya (Emet, Simav), Manisa, Uşak, Nevşehir, and Van. In the Emet district of Kütahya, arsenic levels in drinking water have been reported to reach up to 350 times the limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO), and cancer-related mortality rates are approximately three times higher than in other regions [8, 9, 10, 11].

3. Microbial Bioremediation and Remediation Strategies

3.1. Concept of Bioremediation: Physical and chemical methods used for the remediation of arsenic-contaminated environments are often costly. In contrast, bioremediation is a low-cost and environmentally friendly approach based on the ability of microorganisms to metabolize toxic compounds and remove them from the environment.

3.2. Remediation Mechanisms: Microorganisms and plants manage arsenic through the following mechanisms:

- **Bioaccumulation and Biosorption:** Accumulation within cells or adsorption onto cell surfaces [12]

- **Oxidation and Reduction:** Transformation of arsenic into less toxic or less mobile forms [13]

- **Methylation and Volatilization:** Conversion into gaseous forms for removal from the environment [14]

For example, bacteria such as *Thermus aquaticus* can oxidize arsenic up to 100 times faster than abiotic processes [15].

3.3. Arsenic-Resistant Bacteria: Due to the ubiquitous presence of arsenic in nature, arsenic-resistant bacterial species are widespread. Major resistant genera include:

- *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Achromobacter*
- *Microbacterium*, *Ochrobactrum*, *Halomonas*

These bacteria are among the most promising candidates for arsenic detoxification due to their critical roles in biogeochemical cycles [16].

4. Research Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1. Recent Project Findings: Significant results have been obtained from seven different projects conducted:

- An Anaerobic Bacteriology Laboratory was established at Ege University

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- A total of 81 arsenic-resistant bacterial strains were isolated and identified from contaminated regions, including first records for the Lake Van ecosystem [1]

- Laboratory-scale bioremediation studies were successfully conducted using a Turkish rice variety [1, 17]

4.2. Conclusion: Rapid population growth, increasing pollution, and global warming are making access to safe food and clean water increasingly difficult. Arsenic represents a major threat to ecosystems and, consequently, to human survival. However, despite their microscopic size, microorganisms play an immensely significant role in ecosystems, offering great potential for overcoming this problem.

4.3. Recommendations:

- Isolation of new resistant strains from arsenic-rich environments should be continued

- Molecular mechanisms of arsenic metabolism in microorganisms should be further investigated

- Biotechnological applications should be integrated into agricultural production processes for a sustainable future

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